

Chemical Constituents of the Orchid *Tylostylis discolor* : Occurrence of Flavonoid C-Glucoside in Orchidaceae Plant

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Manuscript received 7 May 1993, accepted 6 July 1993

We reported earlier the isolation of a fairly large number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These compounds mostly include a wide variety of stilbenoids¹, triterpenoids² and steroids³ of biogenic importance. As part of this general programme of research the orchid *Tylostylis discolor* has been chemically investigated, and this has resulted in the isolation of eight compounds of previously known structures. Seven of them were identified with the stilbenoids coelonin^{4,5} (2,7-dihydroxy-4-methoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene), nudol⁶ (2,7-dihydroxy-3,4-dimethoxyphenanthrene), erianthridin⁷ (2,7-dihydroxy-3,4-dimethoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene), gigantol⁸ (3,4'-dihydroxy-3',5'-dimethoxybibenzyl), batatasin-III⁹ (3,3'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl) and flavanthrin⁵ (2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxy-9,9',10,10'-tetrahydrobiphenanthryl) and the triterpenoid lupeol¹⁰ by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., tlc and ir spectra) with their respective

authentic samples isolated earlier in our laboratory from taxonomically related Orchidaceae plants. The remaining compound formed a heptaacetyl derivative with Ac₂O and pyridine. The physical constants and the spectral data of the above compound and its heptaacetyl derivative compared excellently with those reported^{11,12} for vitexin (**1a**) and its heptaacetate (**1b**) respectively, although direct comparison could not be made due to unavailability of authentic samples. The identity of the above compound of *T. discolor* with vitexin (**1a**) was finally confirmed by independent ¹³C nmr spectral analysis of the compound (the δ_c values are virtually identical with those reported¹² earlier) and its heptaacetyl derivative reported in this paper for the first time (Table 1). The degree of protonation of the carbon atoms was determined by DEPT (for **1a**) and APT (for **1b**) experiments. The earlier assignments¹² of the δ_c values of **1a** have now been confirmed by the appropriate shifts observed in the spectrum of **1b**. The appearance of a protonated aromatic carbon signal at δ_c 98.19 which corresponds to C-6 of a 5,7-dihydroxyflavone (C-8 of such compounds shows a high field shift, $\sim \delta_c$ 93-94 as in apigenin¹² (4',5,7-trihydroxyflavone) established the placement of the glucopyranosyl moiety at C-8 in **1a**. In the light of the well-documented observation¹² that glycosylated aromatic carbons of ring A of 5,7-dihydroxyflavone derivatives are shifted down-field by ca 9.8 ppm compared to those of their corresponding nonglycosylated analogues, the down-field shift of C-8 (δ_c 104.64) of **1a** by 10.6 ppm compared to the corresponding carbon atom of apigenin (C-8

1a : R=H

1b : R=Ac

TABLE 1—¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF **1a** AND **1b**

C	1a *	1b **	C	1a *	1b **
2	164.0	161.31	4'	161.19	156.71
3	102.51	108.22	1''	73.43	72.60
4	182.16	175.82	2''	70.88	69.20
4a	104.10 ^d	114.63	3''	78.69	73.66
5	160.44	150.15	4''	70.55	67.98
6	98.19	114.35	5''	81.90	76.40
7	162.60	153.29 ^d	6''	61.32	61.70
8	104.64 ^d	115.46	OCOMe	-	19.83, 20.26, 20.29, 20.36, 20.56, 20.70, 20.80, 167.57, 168.50, 169.22, 169.94.
8a	156.05	152.24 ^d			
1'	121.66	128.46			
2',6'	129.05	127.46			
3',5'	115.87	122.44			

*Spectrum was run in DMSO-d₆ and the chemical shifts were measured with δ_{TMS} = δ_(d6-DMSO) + 39.7 ppm.

**Spectrum was run in CDCl₃ and the chemical shifts were measured with δ_{TMS} = δ_(CDCl₃) + 76.9 ppm.

^dValues are interchangeable within each column.

appeared at δ_c 94.0) further confirmed the placement of the glucopyranosyl moiety at C-8 in **1a**. The alternative formulation of **1a** with the glucopyranosyl moiety at C-6 would have caused the glucosylated carbon (C-6) to resonate at ca δ_c 108–109 as in isoorientenin¹² (3',4',5,7-tetrahydroxy-6-glucopyranosylflavone : C-6 at δ_c 108.7). It is interesting to note that the isolation of vitexin (**1a**) from *T. discolor* constitutes the first report of the occurrence of a C-glycosidic flavone in Orchidaceae plant and is of considerable chemotaxonomic importance.

Experimental

Air-dried whole plant material of *T. discolor* (3 kg) was kept soaked with MeOH (10 l) for 3 weeks. The methanolic extract was collected and concentrated under reduced pressure to ca 100 ml. The above concentrated extract, when kept overnight at room temperature, deposited a solid which was filtered and crystallised from MeOH to give **1a** (12 g, 0.4%), m.p. 265°, [α]_D-14° (pyridine); λ_{max} (EtOH) 217, 273 and 316.5 nm (log ε 4.40, 4.24 and 4.15); ν_{max} 3240 (chelated OH), 3385 (OH), 1660 (chelated C=O), 1570 and 838 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H nmr δ(DMSO-d₆) 3.23–3.85 (6H, m, H-2'', H-3'', H-4'', H-5'' and H₂-6''), 4.68 (1H, d, J,

9.8 Hz, H-1''), 6.27 (1H, s, H-6), 6.78 (1H, s, H-3), 6.88 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 8.02 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 10.37, 10.87 and 13.17 (each 1H, s, disappeared on deuterium exchange, 3 × ArOH). **1a** was acetylated with Ac₂O and pyridine to give the heptaacetyl derivative **1b**, crystallised from a mixture of light petroleum ether and ethyl acetate, m.p. 258°, [α]_D-73° (acetone); λ_{max} (EtOH) 220, 260 and 302.5 nm (log ε 3.99, 4.15 and 4.36); ν_{max} 1250 and 1750 (OAc), 1650 (C=O), 845, 780 and 750 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.73, 1.89, 1.98, 2.08 and 2.34 (each 3H, s, 5 × OAc), 2.41 (6H, s, 2 × OAc), 3.87–4.16 (2H, m, H₂-6''), 4.91 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz, H-1''), 5.22–5.47 (4H, m, H-2'', H-3'', H-4'' and H-5''), 6.67 (1H, s, H-6), 6.77 (1H, s, H-3), 7.38 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 8.06 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-2' and H-6'); MS(EI) *m/z* (rel. int.) 726 (*M*⁺, 2.2), 684 (11.4), 642 (3), 583 (0.5), 541 (0.5), 462 (2), 449 (11), 407 (11), 341 (8), 298 (8), 139 (10), 97 (11), 81 (15), 69 (15), 60 (24) and 43 (100); MS(CI) *m/z* (rel. int.) 727 [(*M*⁺ + 1), 36].

The filtrate obtained after removal of **1a** was diluted with water (500 ml) and the liberated solids were extracted with Et₂O. The Et₂O extract

was fractionated into acidic and neutral parts by treatment with aqueous 2M NaOH solution. The NaOH solution was acidified with concentrated HCl in the cold, and the liberated solids were extracted with Et₂O, washed with water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and the solvent was removed.

The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (100–200 mesh). The early fractions of the petroleum ether-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate afforded a mixture of coelonin, erianthridin and nudol. Repeated chromatography of this mixture gave in the early fractions of petroleum ether-EtOAc (15 : 1) eluate pure erianthridin (0.05 g, 0.0017%), crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 148°. The middle fractions of the same eluate afforded pure nudol (0.06 g, 0.002%), crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 189°. The last few fractions of the above eluate gave pure coelonin (0.09 g, 0.003%), crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 84°.

The later fractions of the petroleum ether-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate from the main column gave a residue containing gigantol and batatasin-III which were separated in the pure state by repeated chromatography; gigantol (0.09 g, 0.003%) and batatasin-III (0.06 g, 0.002%) both obtained as semisolid mass.

The petroleum ether-EtOAc (7 : 1) eluate from the main column afforded flavanthrin (0.03 g, 0.001%) crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 285°.

Chromatography of the neutral fraction of *T. discolor* over silica gel (100–200 mesh) gave in the petroleum ether-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate lupeol (0.12 g, 0.004%), crystallised from petroleum ether-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 215°.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. J. M. Wilson, University of Manchester, U.K., for the mass spectra, and Dr. A. K. Sarkar, University of California, U.S.A. (now at the Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta) for the ¹H nmr spectrum of **1b**. The work was supported by U.G.C., New Delhi.

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